

Impact Factor: 4.9

ISSN: 2181-0664
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664
www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Special Issue 1

2022

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

1 МАХСУС СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
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ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№SI-1 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2022-SI-1>

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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE PREVENTION OF DENTAL CARIES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7404861>

ABSTRACT

One of the most common pathologies, hard tissues of children's teeth, is caries. The main differences between caries in milk teeth and a similar pathological process in permanent teeth are rapid progression and the presence of forms of carious damage unusual for permanent teeth. Therefore, modern measures for the prevention of caries in young children are one of the urgent problems of pediatric dentistry.

Keywords: children, dental caries, risk factors, primary prevention, level of hygiene knowledge.

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ КАРИЕСА ЗУБОВ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Одной из наиболее частых патологий, твёрдых тканей детских зубов, является кариес. Главными отличиями кариеса молочных зубов от аналогичного патологического процесса в зубах постоянных являются быстрое прогрессирование и наличие несвойственных для постоянных зубов форм кариозного повреждения. Поэтому современные мероприятия по профилактике кариеса у детей раннего возраста одна из актуальных проблем детской стоматологии.

Ключевые слова: дети, кариес зубов, факторы риска, первичная профилактика, уровень гигиенических знаний.

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МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАРДА ТИШ КАРИЕСИНИНГ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЁНДАШУВЛАР

АННОТАЦИЯ

Энг кенг тарқалган патологиялардан бири, болалар тишларининг қаттиқ тўқималари - кариес. Сут тишларидаги кариес ва доимий тишлардаги шунга ўхшаш патологик жараён ўртасидаги асосий фарқлар тез ўсиб бориши ва доимий тишлар учун одатий бўлмаган кариес шикастланиш шаклларининг мавжудлиги. Шунинг учун ёш болаларда кариеснинг олдини олиш бўйича замонавий чора-тадбирлар педиатрия стоматологиясининг долзарб муаммоларидан биридир.

Калит сўзлар: болалар, тиш кариеси, хавф омиллари, бирламчи профилактика, гигиена билимлари даражаси.

Introduction. Early childhood caries is an infectious disease of bacterial origin. This is mainly due to social inequalities in oral health and most often affects children from the least privileged segments of the population. Because of its relapsing nature, it is the most common chronic disease in preschool children. Because it shares common risk factors with a number of other chronic conditions (diabetes, obesity), promoting global oral health is essential to achieving favorable overall health.

It has been proven that dental morbidity in childhood and adolescence largely determines the state of people's health in subsequent years of life. For this reason, data on the intensity and prevalence of dental pathology in children are the object of close attention of scientists and practical dentists of Uzbekistan [Akhrorhuzhaev N.Sh., Shamsieva Sh.F., Tajiev Zh.B., 2019; Abduazimova L.A., Mukhtorova M.M. 2021; Zokirkhonova Sh.A. 2021].

A high percentage of children with complications of dental caries is observed in developing countries. In India, complications of early childhood caries (puff >0) were reported in 71.4% of children aged 6 to 72 months [Sharna N., Ramakrishnan M., Samuel V 2019]. In a study conducted in the Philippines, 85% of six-year-old children had a pufa index above zero [Monse B., Heinrich-Weltzien R. 2010]. In the Iranian population of children aged 6 to 12 years, 25.9% had complications of caries, and the average value of pufa was 1.09 [Ramazani N., Rezaei S. 2017]. Deciduous tooth caries rates in Poland are lower than in developing countries, but higher than in more economically developed parts of the European Union [Bencze Z., Mahrouseh N. 2021].

Opydo-Szymaczek J. (2021) In 2016, the national oral health monitoring found that 89.4% of 7-year-old children were affected by caries with an average dmft index of 5.61. In a study by Baginska and Rodakowska, 72.4% of 7-year-old children living in North-Eastern Poland had at least one tooth affected by caries complications (pufa > 0)

Discussion. According to a number of Uzbek scientists, socio-economic risk factors for dental diseases are now increasingly important. It is believed that too young parents, parents with an insufficient level of education do not attach importance to the prevention and maintenance of a high level of children's health, including the prevention of caries and the preservation of healthy teeth in children, the development of habits that contribute to maintaining health. On the other hand, the difficult financial situation of families raising preschoolers does not allow providing children with the necessary items and means of oral hygiene, fluoride supplements and timely medical caries preventive procedures (Kamilova M. 2021; Zokirkhonova S.A. , Kamilov Kh.P. 2020: Okhunzhanova G.K., Rizaev Zh.A. 2020).

The dental health of children largely depends on the ability to follow the basic rules of oral hygiene. As you know, oral hygiene is one of the important methods for preventing caries and periodontal tissue diseases and allows you to eliminate the etiological bacterial factor that causes the development of these pathologies.

Belarusian scientists (Leus P.A. et al. 2020) believe that primary prevention programs for major dental diseases of the teeth and periodontal diseases among the population of the Republic of Belarus are somewhat behind long-term targets, especially in improving the dental health of preschool children. The necessity of integrating dentistry with other medical services for more effective implementation of the program for the prevention of dental caries in young children is substantiated. The data of international and domestic descriptive and analytical epidemiology of dental caries in preschool children and primary school children are analyzed in relation to the ongoing preventive measures for pregnant women and young parents. The results of long-term monitoring of the effectiveness of the work of the Center for Dental Health of Schoolchildren in the Loshitsa microdistrict of the city of Minsk are summarized. The necessity of preventive work among high school students is substantiated, methods of antenatal prevention of dental caries without the intervention of a dentist during pregnancy are proposed. The dynamics of the decrease in the intensity of caries in permanent teeth in first-graders to the level of 0.02-0.07 KPU has been established. The integration of dental with obstetric-gynecological and pediatric services, as well as the involvement of parents, preschool teachers and school teachers in the prevention program, makes it possible to more effectively implement the tasks of preventing dental diseases in children. The peculiarities of antenatal prophylaxis are the education of high school students and pregnant women on the

prevention of caries in newborns and children of the first years of life, as well as the exclusion of the use of unproven methods, especially systemic exposure during pregnancy. In children of the first year of life and preschool age, the development of caries and gingivitis is caused by numerous risk factors, the elimination of which is impossible without the help of medical and nursing staff of maternity hospitals and children's clinics. The integration of dentistry with obstetric-gynecological and pediatric services, as well as the involvement of parents, preschool teachers and school teachers in the prevention program, makes it possible to more effectively implement the tasks of preventing dental diseases in children.

Chinese scientists (Qu X, Houser SH, Tian M, Zhang Q 2022) studied the study of early prevention, the impact of prevention on dental caries and untreated dental caries, and the study of factors associated with PDV among Chinese children under the age of seven years. Numerous risk factors have been associated with early childhood caries (ECC), such as high numbers of cariogenic oral bacteria, frequent consumption of high-sugar foods, insufficient saliva flow, lower fluoride exposure, poor oral hygiene, and low socioeconomic demographic status. . Therefore, the use of complex methods for the prevention of ECC may be more effective. Scientists believe that specific preventive interventions can be divided into passive and active interventions. A well-known passive preventive intervention is community fluoridated water. Compared to passive prevention, active prevention requires the individual to take action to change their lifestyle by including or eliminating bad habits. Early preventive dental visits (PDV) are one of the most important active preventive interventions. Many dentists recommend that parents take their children to the dentist's office when their first tooth erupts or no later than one year old. Early PDVs can provide more effective and less costly dental care than dental care provided in emergency facilities or hospitals. However, there are significant differences in access to early dental care among the population. The age of the first visit to the dentist varies from one to six worldwide. The underutilization of early dental care has been associated with ethnic minorities, lower family income, poorer parental perceptions and attitudes about dental health, less interdisciplinary collaboration, and lower access to dental services.

Understanding these factors is essential to developing strategies to address disparities in the use of early dental care.

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